

Executive Summary:

We are going to run awareness campaign for the youths about the importance of blood donation in our society. “Share Blood-Share Life” is our main organization motto and our organization wants to prevent any disasters resulting from the scarcity of blood.

Organization Description and History:

History of Youth for Blood dates back to 2011. It was in 2011 when called our Founder Mr. Saroj Karki to donate blood for his uncle and Mr. Karki immediately responded to him and helped him by contacting.....to donate blood. Thus, the blood scarcity was fulfilled which further motivated, and realized the importance of such organization to take immediate action for the emergency case on blood scarcity. Further on Mr. Karki initiated a program forming a group of 60 people to discuss on this topic but on the day of meeting only 5 people attended it. From such an incident and support from several people, Youth for Blood was officially registered on as a not-for-profit NGO in Nepal Government.

Youth for Blood has ran several blood donation program on various parts of country through it's branches at 5 districts at Kathmandu Valley, Chitwan, Sunsari, Morang, and Jhapa. In parallel to blood donation program, Youth for Blood has run several multi-dimensional awareness campaigns regarding the issues on the importance of human blood and the necessity, and has cleared several disputes, misunderstanding, and rumors among the general public. According to the statistics of 2017, Youth for Blood has saved above 40000 lives of people, and has earned several awards from reputed national and international organizations.

Background:

Nepal as a developing country has many challenges in itself, and when we analyze it through Health Sector, it is more pathetic than the rest. Mostly, due to road accidents, and lack of proper health care facilities, scarcity of blood is seen as one

of the major factor for the deaths of patients. Matching the blood, weight, and pressure, sugar, chronic heart diseases, and women having menstrual within 7 days before the date of donation, are the major problem we face to make blood donation successful. Due to negative rumors regarding the blood donation, which is deeply rooted on the public are also one of the factors effecting blood donation program.

Project Description:

Our project run blood donation facilitation programs for providing fresh blood to the patients. The patients who face problems in sorting out the blood via blood bank can directly communicate with us or our volunteers who work 27*7 for serving the needy people. Since our organization is not-for-profit, we are totally service oriented and hence we are free of charge. We further educate the people on the issues of blood scarcity and assemble data to create a effective database of blood donors list, which is vital factor in saving the life of patient. Similarly we run street awareness campaign on regular intervals to the pedestrians by distributing pamphlets, posters, and organizing speeches, dramas and many more on the topic of blood donation.

Objectives:

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Project Activities:

To fulfill the objectives of our organization, we are doing following activities:

- **Leadership Training:**

Leadership training to our volunteers is conducted every 2 months to train the volunteers, and interns to provide different skills to be a successful leader. Our leadership program trains them to work under stressful environment and makes them capable to deal with stress and counsel the needy people which develop positive vibes.

- **Organizational Awareness Campaign:**

We run awareness campaign in different schools, colleges, and other organization to educate people from different background regarding blood and blood donation. These campaigns is generally focused to educate and aware the youths, and connect them under common goal to set blood donation as a culture. From such campaign we further extend blood donor list which plays a vital role in saving the life of patients.

- **Street Awareness Campaign:**

Our street awareness campaign educate the local public and pedestrians by distributing posters, pamphlets, and by conducting street dramas and speeches on the topic of blood and the importance of blood donation. Further, it removes the negative rumors that are conceived by the public regarding blood donation. It also helps us to increase the database of donors list, which helps in minimizing the blood scarcity problem in our society.

- **Community Awareness Campaign:**

The volunteers of our organization reach to the general public especially in the remote areas educating them about blood and blood related information, thus, motivating the entire community to donate blood regularly, which helps to set the culture of blood donation. We often go door-to-door educating the people on the importance of blood donation.

- **Creating Blood Donors Database:**

Our organization by various means create a blood donors database to provide effective and convenient database of people of various blood groups, which helps us to take immediate action in the case of blood scarcity to the victims. Our database format is as shown as below:

Donor's Name	Address	Contact	Email	Blood Group	Age	Gender

Through this database we can perform quick response to the needy people within their location for more convenience.

- **Sharing Day:**

Our organization conducts sharing day every Saturday from 11 A.M to 1 P.M, which summarizes the weekly activities done by our organization. Through this day, we are also able to make brief analysis of the strength, weakness, opportunities, and challenges of our organization, which helps us to achieve our organization goal and makes us ready to face any types of future challenges.

The above activities are performed throughout the year irrespective of any circumstances.

Evaluation:

We have our own evaluation team of expert advisors and intellectual people from various backgrounds, who constantly supervise and monitor to determine how efficiently we have, meet our objectives and serve the people.

Conclusion:

Our youth-led organization works on the sector of blood-donation, awareness campaign, and inspiring the youths, which ultimately solves the blood scarcity and

thus has provided an inexplicable service to our country. Till 2017, our organization had saved above 40000 lives of patients.

Budget:

Expenditure Category	Fund Needed	Total
Materials		
Utilities		
TADA		
Rent		
Intern Expenses		
Volunteer Expenses		
Miscellaneous Expenses		